

Terpenoids. Part LXIII: New Synthesis of Dehydro- α -Curcumene

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5-Methyl-1-(p-tolyl)-4-hexen-1-one, obtained from ethyl p-toluate by reaction with methyl sulphanyl carbanion and subsequent alkylation and hydrogenolysis of the resulting product, when submitted to Wittig reaction with methylene phosphorane, affords dehydro- α -curcumene.

IN continuation of our previous work^{1,2} on the syntheses of terpenoids through a new pathway involving the formation of β -ketosulphoxides and their further alkylation and reduction to provide suitable ketones to function as appropriate intermediates, we report a new synthesis of the title compound in the present communication.

Dehydro- α -curcumene, a monocyclic sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, has been recently isolated from *T. orientalis* wood oil³ by Tomita and co-workers who assigned it the constitution (1) from correlation with α -curcumene. This constitution has been confirmed through a synthesis⁴. A new synthesis has now been achieved by us through the following sequence of reactions.

Ethyl *p*-toluate (II), was treated with methylsulphinyl carbanion, obtained from sodium hydride and dimethylsulphoxide⁵ to form ω -methylsulphinyl-*p*-acetophenone (III) as a white crystalline solid in 88% yield. The β -ketosulphoxide (III) was alkylated with 1-bromo-3-methyl-2-butene in dimethylformamide according to the reported procedure⁶. The methylsulphinyl group in the resulting product was reduced by hydrogen with zinc-acetic acid⁷ to afford the ketone (IV) which deposited as red needles after crystallisation from ethanol, forming a 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative, forming a 2,4-DNP, m.p. 242°-242.5°. The ketone IV was finally submitted to the Wittig reaction⁸ with methylene triphenylphosphorane to afford I. The synthetic sample was characterised through the comparison of its I.R. and N.M.R. spectral data given for the natural dehydro- α -curcumene³.

Experimental

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer Infrared 337 using thin liquid films. Microanalysis was done by Mr. L. K. Khullar, Panjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh.

ω -(Methyl sulphanyl)-*p*-methyl acetophenone (III) :

To the methyl sulphanyl carbanion prepared from sodium hydride (1.46 g) and dimethyl sulphoxide (30 ml) anhyd. tetrahydrofuran (30 ml) was added and the contents cooled in an ice-bath. This was followed by the dropwise addition with stirring of ethyl *p*-toluate (II; 5 g). After stirring for 1 hr more at room temp. the reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The pale solid left after the removal of the solvent was recrystallised from ethyl acetate to furnish (VI; 5.2 g) as colourless needles m.p. 106°. (Lit.⁹ m.p. 105°-6°) in 87% yield. (Found : C, 61.20; H, 6.30; S, 16.43. C₁₀H₁₂O₂S requires : C, 61.12; H, 6.17; S, 16.31%). I.R. (Nujol) : 1690 (carbonyl), 1010-1040 (sulphinyl) and 1600, 1180, 1120, 812 and 720 cm⁻¹ (1 : 4-disubstituted benzene).

5-Methyl-1-(*p*-tolyl)-4-hexen-1-one (IV) :

Compound III (4.5 g) in dimethyl formamide (21 ml) was added to a cooled slurry of sodium hydride (0.55 g) in dimethyl formamide (63 ml). After the addition, the contents were stirred at room temp. till the evolution of hydrogen had ceased. The reaction mixture was again cooled and 1-bromo-3-methyl-2-butene (3.5 g) introduced slowly and with stirring. After continuing the stirring for half an hour at ordinary temp., the reaction mixture was worked up in the manner already described. The residue left after solvent evaporation was kept under reduced pressure for an hour to furnish the alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (3.7 g) which was not isolated as such but directly dissolved in absolute ethanol (6.4 ml) and glacial acetic acid (4.2 ml). The solution was added in about half an hour to a rapidly stirred mixture of zinc dust (4.5 g) in the same volumes of the same solvent mixtures keeping the temperature below 30°. Stirring was continued

for 4 hr after the addition was complete. The suspended solids were removed by filtration and washed thoroughly with benzene. The combined filtrate was diluted with water (30 ml) and powdered sodium carbonate (8 g) was added to neutralise the excess of acetic acid and the extract was washed successively with saturated solutions of sodium bicarbonate (25 ml) and mercuric chloride (5%; 50 ml). The solvent was removed and the residue chromatographed over alumina (30 g) using (1 : 9) benzene-petroleum ether mixture as eluent. The product was further purified by vacuum distillation to furnish the ketone (IV; 2.8 g) in 60% yield, b.p. 107°-108°/3 mm., η_D^{37} 1.4953. The ketone gave a single spot on t.l.c. (solvent system, benzene-hexane, 1 : 1). (Found : C, 83.10; H, 8.89. C₁₄H₁₈O requires C, 83.13; H, 8.97%).

The above ketone formed a red dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative by the sulphuric acid method. The derivative on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 242°-242.5°. (Found : N 14.43. C₂₀H₂₂N₄O₄ requires : N, 14.65). γ_{max} : 3010, 1695, 1595, 1120, 812 and 720 cm⁻¹.

6-Methyl-2-(*p*-tolyl)-1,5-heptadiene (I) :

To the methylene triphenyl phosphorane, prepared from sodium hydride (0.12 g) in dimethyl sulphoxide (3 ml) and methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide (2 g) in dimethyl sulphoxide (5 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere was added the ketone (IV; 1 g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (5 ml). The contents were stirred and heated for one hour at 50° and left overnight at room temp. The usual work up of the reaction mixture gave a residue which was passed through alumina column (10 g) and eluted with petroleum ether. The hydrocarbon fraction obtained was finally distilled under reduced pressure to afford dehydro- α -curcumene (I, 0.6 g) in 60% yield, b.p. 110°-15°/4-5 mm., η_D^{37} 1.4914. It gave a single spot on t.l.c. (solvent : hexane). (Found : C, 89.62; H, 10.04. C₁₅H₂₀ requires : C, 89.94; H, 10.06%).

I.R. spectrum of the synthetic sample showed absorption peaks at 3070, 1630, 1570, 1520, 1450, 1380, 1185, 1115, 1015, 888, 822, 775 and 730 cm⁻¹ in agreement with the literature³.

N.M.R. spectrum gave the following characteristic signals τ : 2.8 (m, 4H, aromatic); 4.8 (bs, 1H, trisubstituted double bond); 5.05 (bs, 2H, terminal methylene group); 7.65 (s, 3H methyl group directly linked to the benzene ring) and 8.6 (d, 6H, two methyl groups on the double bond) in close agreement with the reported values³.

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